

STRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES
OF SiC-PARTICLE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM-ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Metal-matrix composites containing 0-20 wt% SiC-particles of relatively small sizes ranging from 7 to 29 μm were produced using the compocasting technique. Metallographic examination shows that the distribution of the particles is homogeneous for the coarse particles whereas some agglomeration occurs in the case of the smaller ones. The mechanical properties in tension and compression were evaluated at both room and elevated temperature and correlations were established with the volume fraction and the size of the particles. The different behaviour of the composites in tension and compression is attributed to the presence of residual stresses in the particles and at the particle-matrix interface. This difference was however found to depend on the state of the material, solution-treated or aged. Moreover, the experimental results suggest that the aging treatment should be different for the matrix and the composites in order to achieve the best mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium-matrix composites are becoming important in many applications especially in the aircraft and aerospace industry and now they are also desirable in the automobile industry. Many efforts have been directed to develop high performance composites with high strengths and moduli [1]. For economical reasons, aluminium matrices are mostly reinforced by low cost refractory fibers such as SiC or Alumina. These fibers have been successfully incorporated into the matrix using various of techniques such as powder metallurgy, stir-casting, compocasting or infiltration.

Few composites with particle additions are developed and their purpose was firstly to increase the wear resistance of the alloys [2]. The particle size was indeed found to have an important role in the wear resistance, whereas its effect on the mechanical properties was not yet well investigated. Comparative tensile properties between SiC whiskers and particulate reinforced Al-alloys were recently studied [3] but the results showed some discrepancy.

In the present study, aluminium matrix composites have been developed using low cost SiC particles incorporated in the matrix by mechanical stirring in the semi-solid zone. The aim of this paper is to study the role of both the particle size and volume fraction on the mechanical properties, and for this purpose tension and compression tests were performed at room and elevated temperature both in the solution-treated and aged conditions. Such tests will thus give some useful indication about the interest of using SiC particles as reinforcement in Al-alloys.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Al-7% Si alloys containing 0.25 to 0.40% Mg were reinforced by SiC particles introduced during mechanical stirring in the mushy zone where solid and liquid are coexisting. After the completion of addition of the particles, mechanical stirring was continued in the mushy zone for about 15 min. in order to increase the wettability between the SiC particles and the liquid metal and complete the homogenization of the mixture.

The composite was thereafter poured at 700°C into the preheated mould of a squeeze casting machine in which the solidification is accomplished under high pressure of about 100 MPa.

The matrix alloys were modified by strontium at 700°C before the addition of the SiC particles. This modification avoids the formation of very large and plate-like particles of eutectic silicon which have deleterious effect on the mechanical properties of the alloys.

Ingots were fabricated with different particle sizes (P.S) of 7, 13 and 29 μm , and with also different weight percents of about 0, 1, 10 and 20, corresponding respectively about to 0, 0.85, 8.5 and 17 volume percents.

Mechanical Test

Tensile and compression test specimens were machined from the squeeze-cast ingots. Cylindrical specimens of 6.00 mm diameter and 43 mm length between the threaded heads were used for the tensile tests. The compression specimens were cylindrical of 8.0 mm dia. and 12.0 mm height.

The tensile and compression specimens were submitted to solid solution heat treatment at 540°C for 8h then quenched in iced water. One part was tested in the solution-treated condition at room temperature. The other part was submitted to aging at 160°C for 4h and air cooled. The conditions of both the solution and aging heat-treatment were chosen as those proposed for the starting Al-Si alloy. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature, at a constant crosshead speed of 0.26 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The deformation of the specimens was measured by an extensometer mounted on the specimen over a gauge length of 20 mm.

Compression tests were conducted also at room temperature with the same machine as for the tensile tests. The crosshead speed was fixed to be 0.5 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ during the test.

Tensile tests were also carried out at elevated temperature at 160° and 300°C. The specimens were maintained at the required temperature for 10 min . before the test. The crosshead speed was constant at 0.26 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The stress-strain behaviour at high temperature was deduced from the recorded load-time curves.

Structural Observation

The distribution of the particles was observed using S.E.M. after the samples have been polished and deeply attacked in a NaOH solution.

The fracture surfaces were also observed by S.E.M. after the rupture of the tensile test specimens in both the solution-treated (S.T) and aged (A) condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structures

Figure 1 shows the microstructure of the composites with different particle sizes. It can be seen that the distribution of the particles in the matrix is usually homogeneous (fig.1 a,b,c), whatever the volume fraction. However for the composites containing large volume fraction of 7 μm SiC particles, agglomerates are found such as that shown in figure 1d. Such agglomerates probably form during the fabrication process, particularly during the complete remelting of the material before pouring. The figure shows also the homogeneous distribution of the Si which looks globular due to both the Sr modification and the heat-treatment.

Fig.1 - SEM photomicrographs of composites containing SiC particles ; a) 10 wt.%, 29 μm ; b) 10 wt.%, 13 μm ; c) 10 wt.%, 7 μm , and d) 20 wt.%, 7 μm

Tensile properties at Room Temperature

Effect of volume fraction and particle size on proof stress

Figure 2 shows the effect of the volume fraction of SiC particles on the proof stress taken at 0.2% strain (σ_V) of Al-Si/SiCp composites tested in the S.T condition, for different particle sizes. It can be seen that σ_V increases as the volume fraction (V_p) of SiC particles increases. This effect however depends on the particle size. For example, for a volume fraction of 8.5%, the increase of the proof stress is higher for the 13 μm particles than that for the 7 and 29 μm , whereas at a volume fraction of 17%, the composite with 29 μm particles shows higher proof stress than the others.

Similar results have been also obtained from the composites tested in the A condition. These results are seen in figure 3 which shows the effect of the particle size on the proof stress. It can be seen that the proof stress increases as the particle size increases up to a critical value after which the proof stress starts to decrease. This critical value of particle size tends to shift to the right (larger particle size) as the volume fraction increases.

The results shown in figures 2 and 3 thus demonstrate that, both the volume fraction and the particle size control the proof stress of the composites which means that the degree of hardening is a function of the interparticle spacing whose value is controlled by the distribution of the particles. For small particles, as the volume fraction is increased, the SiC particles tend to be agglomerated as a consequence of the fabrication process resulting in lower strength than expected for an homogeneous distribution. For bigger particles such agglomeration does not occur and the composite thus shows an important increase of the proof stress compared to the matrix alloy.

The same behaviour is found for the aged composites, but with higher strength values due to the presence of very fine Mg_2Si precipitates which are formed during the aging process.

Fig.2 - Effect of SiC content on tensile proof stress for solution-treated composites of different particle sizes.

Fig.3 - Effect of SiC particle size on tensile proof stress for aged composites.

Effect of the volume fraction and particle size on ductility

The effect of the volume fraction of SiC particles on ductility (strain measured at fracture ϵ_f) of the composite alloys tested in the S.T condition is shown in figure 4. It can be seen that ϵ_f is strongly decreased with increasing volume fraction of SiC particles and this decrease is more pronounced for the smaller sizes.

The effect of the particle size on the ductility (failure strain) for the aged composites is shown in figure 5. As for the S.T specimens, the ductility of the composites is always smaller than that of the matrix. In this case however, the fracture strain seems to slightly increase as the size of the particles increases.

Fig.4 - Effect of SiC content on failure strain for solution-treated composites of different particle sizes.

Fig.5 - Effect of SiC particle size on failure strain for aged composites.

From these results in both the S.T and A conditions, it is concluded that SiC particle addition leads always to embrittlement of the matrix alloy. The particles, which are of irregular shapes, act as areas of local stress concentration which make crack initiation and propagation to occur especially when agglomeration takes place as in the case of large volume fraction of small particles.

Effect of aging of mechanical properties

In order to evaluate the response of the composites to the aging treatment, the increase of the proof stress for the aged specimens σ_{V_A} compared to the solution treated ones $\sigma_{V_{ST}}$ was calculated ($\sigma_{V_A} - \sigma_{V_{ST}}$) and this difference is plotted in figure 6 as a function of V_p the volume fraction of SiC particles V_p for different particles sizes. The figure shows that ($\sigma_{V_A} - \sigma_{V_{ST}}$) is higher for the composites than for the matrix. It increases initially as V_p increases and decreases thereafter for large volume fraction of particles V_p .

As the matrix alloy and the composites were aged for the same time at the same temperature (4h at 160°C which is the standard heat treatment for the matrix) the previous results seem to indicate that this treatment is not the optimum one for the composites. The decrease of the proof stress at large V_p suggests that these composites age faster than both the matrix and the composites with low V_p , and consequently 4h at 160°C corresponds to an overaging of the composites with large V_p . Similar results were reported in SiC/Al composites [4] as well as B_4C/Al [5]. The high dislocation density generated during quenching of the specimens from the temperature of the solution-treatment as a consequence of the mismatch

between the thermal expansion coefficients of the matrix and the particles, affects the effective diffusivity of the matrix thus accelerating the aging reaction.

Fig.6 - Increase in tensile proof stress due to aging treatment as a function of SiC content for different particle sizes.

Compressive Properties at Room Temperature

The compression tests conducted at room temperature give similar results to those in tension for the evolution of the stresses as a function of the volume fraction and the size of the SiC particles.

Comparison between compression and tension was made by plotting the difference between the tensile and compressive proof stresses $\sigma_t - \sigma_c$ as a function of the volume fraction of the SiC particles in both the S.T and A conditions. This plot is given in figure 7. It shows that :

- The compressive stress is higher than the tensile one for the matrix in the S.T condition, whereas the reverse is observed for the composites.
- In the A condition, the compressive stress of the matrix is still higher than the tensile one but the difference is slightly smaller.
- All the aged composites show higher compressive stresses than the tensile ones.
- The magnitude of $(\sigma_Y^t - \sigma_Y^c)$ depends on the volume fraction and the size of the particles.

The results given in figure 7 are rather difficult to explain but residual stresses created in the specimens during cooling to room temperature, have to be considered for any explanation.

In fact residual stresses can be expected in such materials on two different scales :

- Macroscale residual stresses originated from the temperature gradient produced by quenching. Such stresses are tensile in the center of the specimens and compressive at the surface. They are created in both the matrix and the composites and their magnitude depends on the quenching conditions (temperature and cooling rate) and the size of the specimens.

- Microscale residual stresses due to the mismatch between the thermal expansion coefficients of the matrix and the particles. These stresses are compressive in the particles and tensile in the matrix. Their magnitude depends on the quenching conditions (temperature and cooling rate), the size and the volume fraction of the particles.

Fig.7 - Difference between the tensile and compressive proof stress as a function of SiC content for aged (open symbols) and solution-treated (closed symbols) composites of different particle sizes.

For the matrix, either in the S.T or A conditions, the macroscale stresses are the only ones and the material can thus support slightly higher stress in compression than in tension. This result is in agreement with the literature.

For the composites, an inverse behaviour is observed for the S.T specimens. In this case, the specimens are quenched from 540°C and this leads to high residual compressive microscale stresses in the particles. The higher observed tensile proof stress of the material supports the conclusion that the behaviour of such composites is controlled by the fracture strength of the particles which is thus higher in tension than in compression. Indeed the soft matrix is restrained from deformation by the rigid interface of the hard particles leading to internal shear stress inside the particles. As the loading continues to increase, the shear stress increases up to the fracture stress of the particles, causing the composite material to yield. Such particle fracture was clearly observed on the fracture surface of the tensile specimens. An example is given in figure 8.

For the aged composites, the microscale stresses are much smaller than in the S.T specimens and the material in this case behaves more or less as the matrix alloy. Larger differences between compressive and tensile stresses are however observed but this result is not yet fully understood.

Fig.8 - SEM photomicrograph showing fracture surface of a solution-treated composite, 10wt.% of 29 μm SiC.

Tensile Properties at Elevated Temperature

Tensile tests were performed at 160°C and 300°C for the various materials and figure 9 shows the evolution of the proof stress σ_y as a function of temperature for the matrix and the composite with 8.5 and 17 volume percent of 29 μm SiC particles. All the specimens were in the aged conditions before the test. Stress decreases with increasing temperature

Fig.9 - Effect of test temperature on tensile proof stress for the matrix and the composites containing different volume fractions of 29 μm SiC particles.

Fig.10 - Effect of the test temperature on failure strain for the matrix and the composites containing different volume fractions of 29 μm SiC particles.

whatever V_p and at 300°C the stresses are almost identical for the matrix and the composites. Similar results were obtained for the composites with 7 μm and 13 μm SiC particles. Figure 10 shows the evolution of fracture strain as a function of temperature for the matrix and the composite with 29 μm SiC particles. Fracture strain is observed to slightly decrease for the matrix alloy whereas it remains almost constant for the composite. It is however much smaller than that of the matrix.

The results concerning the tensile tests at elevated temperature seem to be quite surprising since ductility generally increases as temperature increases. In this case however, the matrix alloy was modified by Sr addition and this treatment considerably increase the ductility at room temperature compared to the non modified materials. Heating at 160°C or 300°C thus leads to some kind of overaging of the material with coarsening of the Si particles thus decreasing ductility.

CONCLUSION

1. Al-Si alloys containing up to 20 wt% SiC particles can be successfully produced by the combined processing route of compositing followed by squeeze-casting.
2. Distribution of the particles is generally homogeneous except for large volume fractions of small particles for which agglomeration forms during the fabrication process.
3. SiC particles appreciably improve strength of the alloys and decrease ductility. These influences however depend on the volume fraction and the size of the particles.
4. Comparison between strengths of solution-treated and aged materials for different particle volume fraction suggests that aging occurs faster for the composite than for the matrix.
5. The difference between tensile and compressive stresses depends on the treatment of the composite. It can be analysed in terms of residual stresses formed during quenching of the material.
6. Evaluation of the strength of the composite at elevated temperature shows that the particles become less efficient for the reinforcement of the Al-Si alloys than at room temperature.

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